

IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION AND SPORTS

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The world we live in seems to be changing at a very fast pace. Although the most prominent examples of this change are in technology, it is clear that it actually permeates all aspects of life. When evaluated from an international perspective, it can be said that borders have almost disappeared due to the influence of technology in many areas, especially in economic, social and cultural areas. The process that has been identified as the source of all these changes and interactions is today called globalization. The word globalization is often used as a multidimensional concept. Today, with the process of globalization in many fields, distant places have become close. What happens in one country at one end of the world affects another country at the other end.

The impact of globalization is evident in the field of sports, as in many other fields. Sport is becoming industrialized day by day. Live broadcasts of various sports competitions have a large audience all over the world. Many foreign athletes change their citizenship and participate in national teams. In addition, it can be said that sport is also affected by globalization, just as globalization affects the field of sports. Worldwide, the common language created by concepts such as performance, competition, and records in sports serves to accelerate globalization.

Keywords: Globalization, Sport, Technology

Enter

The process of globalization that we are experiencing today is causing various changes in many areas. This process is rapidly developing with all positive and negative approaches. The impact of the wind of globalization is felt in all cells of the sports field, as in many areas in all countries of the world. Sport has become an integral part of societies all over the world; Most people incorporate daily sports activities into their lives, such as fitness, healthy living, and recreation. Furthermore, individuals are involved in sports in some way, even as spectators or fans. Today, when the process of globalization is very fast, the echoes of mass culture created through mass media are clearly manifested in the field of sports, which has taken its share from this process by acquiring a mass, industrial, commercial, politicized and scientific tone. In this study, we have tried to explore the reflection of the difficult nature of globalization in the field of sports and how sports are actually affected by the acceleration of globalization.

The New World Order as an Image of the Global Village

According to some social scientists, the phenomenon of globalization is not a new phenomenon, and it is argued that globalization began in the form of trade relations and military invasions from the millennium BC, even before modern capitalism. "In fact, if we look at the history of all countries, we see that their only goal is to dominate the world and its

wealth. Therefore the history of globalization; "It can be traced back to the rise of religions and empires."

The origin of the word global began 400 years ago. However, the emergence of the concept of globalization dates back to the 1960s. Although it was frequently used in the 1980s, by the 1990s it was seen that every economic, political and social phenomenon could not be explained without emphasizing globalization; Nowadays, globalization is at the center of people's lives.

There are different approaches and views on the definition and meaning of globalization. For some, globalization is a happy ending in which liberalism declares its victory, while for others it is a transformed form of imperialism, "capitalism as a common way of life becomes widespread and capital dominates globally."

"Globalization essentially involves the disappearance of national borders and the increasing integration of countries into one another." As a general definition, the concept of globalization means the strengthening of economic, political, social and cultural relations throughout the world.

The process of globalization is taking place in almost every sphere, which is starting to direct individuals and societies towards a certain point. It seems impossible to stay out of this new structure. This structure is a process from personal life to business life, from financial plans to educational life. "Increasing changes in the last quarter of the twentieth century turned the world into a 'global village' and increased the importance of global marketing."

What happens anywhere in the world increasingly affects what happens in other parts of the world. "In other words, any decision made by local groups or communities and/or any practice they carry out will have consequences in other parts of the world."

The effects and consequences of the global age range from economic to political and cultural dimensions. "Economic globalization is a phenomenon in which everything produced is quickly sold to the consumer market, the mobility of goods and services exceeds geographical boundaries, and the fluidity of capital increases."

In the process of globalization, societies are becoming closer together and cultural exchange is developing rapidly thanks to mass media. "Technological changes have also led to the emergence of a new global media industry, and production is regionalized rather than confined to a particular location."

The phenomenon of globalization, created by changes in communication technologies and common living spaces, is changing local customs, transcending national borders and directing people to a common way of life in many ways.

Along with positive views of the globalization process, "We are witnessing discourses of almost all hopelessness." The reason for these different views is that "There are social groups that benefit from the development of globalization, just as there are social groups. groups affected by globalization."

Globalization of sports

Sport, as a social phenomenon, entered the social life in different ways, made individuals dependent on it as an active (participant) or passive (spectator) and managed to maintain the interest of society. From 1945 to 1989-1991. During the collapse of the Soviet Union, the competition between the Western world led by the United States of America and the Eastern world led by the Soviet Union became a determining factor in power relations in many areas. "Sports actually played an important role in testing the power and competition

between the two poles in a non-war environment during this period, because sports competitions meant war without death. "Sports achievements were linked to the success of systems, and sports were seen as an effective means of promoting regimes and countries."

Nowadays, sport has become important both in terms of tourism and branding of cities and countries. In the process of globalization, sport is becoming an increasingly important issue due to its characteristics as a long-term tool and measure of international changes. Major sporting events have come to be seen as valuable beacons through which countries can present themselves to a global audience of investors, tourists and consumers.

Sport has the power to appeal to all societies on earth, regardless of the social, cultural structures or governance styles of nations. Taking this feature into account, we can see that globalization is taking place at a great pace in the field of sports. As a result of the globalization process showing its attractive nature in the field of sports, common rules, principles and goals for all countries in a single structure have become crucial. This phenomenon brings together people of different cultures, religions, languages or political preferences to participate in sports activities on a common basis.

Today's live televised Champions League football matches are eagerly watched by the world's public. Given the influence of official and commercial power on society in various ways, the popular culture created by televised sporting events is very important. takes place.

So much so that today, major international sports organizations such as the Olympic Games or the World Cup do not have an extensive media army, national flags do not fly, national anthems do not play, politicians do not participate in ceremonies, competitors wear the national dress of their choice instead of wear clothes, it seems difficult to imagine.

Sport is also seen as an area that permeates social life and contributes to the emergence of culture and interaction in society. According to this view, sport is "a system of symbols used to produce dominant ideologies and ensure social consent." The process of globalization, on the one hand, prepares the ground for these ideological developments, and on the other hand, the production of sports products, marketing, etc. It represents a very important share of the world economy by providing the employment needed to carry out these activities. Activities such as the use of underdeveloped countries in the production of new sports equipment (cheap labor), the management of world organizations by various international sports federations, the transfer of athletes from different nations to professional teams, popularization of sports competitions. The achievements achieved in the international arena through various advertisements and publications are among the trends of globalization in sports.

The biggest factor accelerating the globalization of sports, as in other industries, is the rapid development of technology. Although the mass media has virtually eliminated the concept of distance, it has made cultural interaction easier than ever before. It changed social structures and created a mass culture, and as a result it created a homogenous culture.

The importance of electronic mass media as an engine in the globalization of sports is a fact that should be emphasized. The development of technology and mass media is not the only condition, but one of the leading conditions in explaining globalization and sports processes. Today, many national and international broadcasting organizations reach millions of people worldwide by broadcasting sports events and commercials.

The Marxist view considers sport as an organized sphere of commercial activity in a capitalist society. In addition, another ideological effect of sports is to force the working class to forget about exploitation and accept the values and ideologies that prevail in society. and the workplace is very effective in terms of the continuity of the capitalist system.

The capitalist system in the world does not prevent the globalization of sports; On the contrary, sport has an inevitable connection with many capitalist companies because of the income it provides. Many local and multinational companies that want to participate in this industry have a wide range of income from the income of broadcasting live competitions to individual sponsorships. or team sponsorship agreements, in competition. Here, in addition to the impact of globalization on sports, it can be said that sports also accelerate globalization and actually serve it. The effect of any advertisement or advertisement on sports theme is such that it can attract people all over the world regardless of their religion, language, race or culture. Many multinational companies are aware of this power of sports and are investing heavily to use this situation to their company's advantage.

Today, mass sports/entertainment culture around the world is built around soccer; When it comes to entertainment or sports, the first thing that comes to mind is football. Football, which has become a global industry, differs from all other sports in this respect. "Football is one of the important stages and phases of globalization." Football's most important governing body, the Fédération Internationale de Football Association (FIFA) has more members (208 members) than the United Nations (193 members). Although football is the sport most affected by the changes in sports due to globalization, there have been significant changes in the field of sports in general. With the growth of the sports market, the number of countries receiving and sending athlete immigration has also increased.

The inconvenient truth is; While there are many virtues associated with the globalization movement in sports, globalization is not all positive. The phenomenon of consumption, which is growing in waves under the influence of globalization, did not ignore sports. In addition to being a game, sporting events have become an economic engine. He noted that "people and organizations in the industry have changed over time, with clubs becoming businesses and fans and spectators becoming consumers." Film, music and football/sports, shaped by capitalism and part of popular culture, now tell global stories. Sports networks such as football and basketball, which are popular all over the world, have become tools of market logic according to the trends and preferences of countries.

The positive and negative aspects of the phenomenon of globalization in sports are complicated by changes in sports in the conditions of capitalism and economic relations. Technological changes are developing at a speed that almost eliminates the impossible in sports, which leads to a change in some values. Athletes today are able to compete with more ergonomic equipment along with advancing technology. In this way, it became possible to break records that seemed impossible in the past. This situation contributes to the development of sports, but on the other hand, it causes athletes to become machines, striving to win and set new records. Athletes who think that success is only about winning are exposed to aggression, doping, match-fixing, etc. may exhibit behavior outside of moral values. The negative effects of globalization are felt more in underdeveloped or developing nation states. Developing countries aim to generate high income by spending less on sports. The desire to achieve results in sports; Organization of sports events for all by investing in sports, development of amateur sports and sports culture, increase of sports recreation facilities are

of priority. However, this logic of globalization does not work as expected in sports. Because it is unrealistic to expect success in sports without investing in it.

Discussion and conclusion

The most criticized social consequence of globalization is the social injustice or inequality that occurs throughout the world and within countries. Although globalization has brought significant changes in the fields of international economy, culture, and telecommunications, the degree of utilization of these changes is not the same for everyone. "While globalization has brought great gains to some people, the vast majority of the world's population has not benefited from these gains." Similarly, globalization in the field of sports ensures that the product reaches a worldwide sports audience.

However, on the other hand, it is a fact that cannot be ignored that people all over the world do not have equal access to this service. As a result, it can be seen that globalization shows its positive and negative aspects in the field of sports as well as in other fields. It can be said that sport contributes greatly to globalization due to its popularity and common language. Today, many multinational companies aim to increase the effectiveness of their products by using famous athletes or sports themes in their advertising and promotions. Promotions and organizations using sports content are accepted worldwide on every platform. In this sense, it can be said that sport serves to accelerate globalization, and globalization and sport actually interact.

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